

Effect of complexation on herbicidal character of Metribuzin with copper(II)

Rajeeva Ranjan, Punam Verma, Rekha Rani, N. C. Bhattacharjee and Shivadhar Sharma*

University Department of Chemistry, Magadh University, Bodh Gaya-823 234, Bihar, India

E-mail : sharma.shivadhar@gmail.com

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Abstract : Metribuzin derived from precursor triazinone i.e. 4-amino-6-tert.-butyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazine-5-one has been used for complexation with copper(II) with empirical formula $[\text{Cu}(\text{MBN})_2\text{X}_2]$ where MBN is Metribuzin i.e. 4-amino-6-tert.-butyl-3-methylthio-1,2,4-triazine-5-one and X stands for Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- and ClO_4^- . The newly synthesized complexes have been characterized by microanalysis, IR spectroscopy, molar conductivity, magnetic moment and electronic spectra. The various crystal field parameters like $D_{q(xy)}$, $D_{q(z)}$, D_s and D_t have been derived from their electronic spectra. The positive values of D_s and D_t are indicative of tetragonal elongation along Z-axis of octahedral symmetry of copper(II) complexes. The herbicidal character of copper(II) complexes has been compared with that of Metribuzin and it has been inferred from the results that herbicidal character of Metribuzin gets enhanced in copper(II) complexes.

Keywords : Herbicidal characters, Metribuzin, tetragonal elongation.

Introduction

The nitrogen heterocycles have invited the attention of synthetic organic chemists because of their antioxidant, antibacterial and antifungal activities¹⁻⁵. Particularly triazines have shown interesting pharmacological properties⁶⁻¹⁰. Investigation on potential herbicidal activities of triazine derivatives has been started long-long ago^{11,12}. Since then a good number of triazine derivatives like simazin, ametryn, cyprazine, Metribuzin etc. were evaluated for weed control¹³⁻¹⁶. Metribuzin is distinct from symmetrical triazines such as atrazine, simazin, amytryn etc. in which the central ring structure had alternative nitrogen and carbon atoms whereas Metribuzin has two nitrogen atoms and two carbon atoms adjacent to each other.

Metribuzin

Its pharmacokinetic studies reveal its non-carcinogenic nature to human being¹⁷. Metribuzin has

been used as a potential herbicide since a long^{18,19}. Generally, the biological activities of a biomolecule get changed after complexation with a metal ion as many metal ions also play an essential role in biological systems^{20,21}. Various bioinspired copper complexes have been reported as biomimetic model and chemotherapeutics²². Keeping these perspective in mind, therefore, we have chosen Cu^{II} ions for complexation with Metribuzin along with secondary ligands like Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- and ClO_4^- . We report herein the synthesis structure and herbicidal character of Cu^{II} complexes with Metribuzin.

Result

The percentage composition of the complexes obtained from their microanalysis has been given in Table 1. On the basis of percentage composition, the complexes were formulated as $[\text{Cu}(\text{MBN})_2\text{X}_2]$ where MBN = Metribuzin and X = Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- and ClO_4^- . The molar conductivity values of complexes in DMF solution of 10^{-3} M concentration fall in the range of $16-22 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which indicate the nonelectrolytic nature of complexes^{22,23}.

Table 1. % composition of Cu^{II} complexes

Complexes	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Calcd. (Found)						λ_m	μ (B.M.)
			Cu	C	H	N	S	Cl/Br		
[Cu(MBN) ₂ Cl ₂]	Bluish green	211	11.38 (11.03)	34.16 (34.34)	4.98 (4.81)	19.92 (19.80)	11.38 (11.14)	12.45 (12.22)	18	1.90
[Cu(MBN) ₂ Br ₂]	Light green	209	9.81 (9.62)	29.44 (29.62)	4.29 (4.18)	17.17 (17.01)	9.81 (9.70)	24.53 (24.33)	22	1.89
[Cu(MBN) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Green	213	10.38 (10.16)	31.16 (31.42)	4.54 (4.21)	22.74 (22.52)	10.38 (10.16)	–	16	1.89
[Cu(MBN) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂]	Deep green	208	10.49 (10.30)	39.34 (39.72)	5.57 (5.21)	18.36 (18.10)	10.49 (10.25)	–	18	1.91
[Cu(MBN) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	Bluish green	213	9.27 (9.05)	27.82 (27.98)	4.08 (3.96)	16.23 (16.11)	9.27 (9.08)	10.14 (10.00)	18	1.91

Infrared spectra and point of ligation :

The free ligand, Metribuzin absorbs at 3490 cm⁻¹ and 3385 cm⁻¹ with medium intensity due to $\nu_{\text{asy}} \text{NH}_2$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{NH}_2$ stretching vibrations respectively²⁴. It is further substantiated by the appearance of a medium band at 1585 cm⁻¹ due to δNH_2 ²⁵. The $\nu_{\text{asy}} \text{NH}_2$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{NH}_2$ suffer red shift in the IR spectra of complexes and appear at 3460–3465 cm⁻¹ and 3330–3340 cm⁻¹ respectively. It shows the coordination of nitrogen of NH₂ group of Metribuzin to Cu^{II} metal ion in all the complexes. The strong band at 2960 cm⁻¹ and a medium band 2870 cm⁻¹ are discernible to $\nu_{\text{asy}} \text{CH}_3$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{CH}_3$ stretching vibrations of t-butyl group of free ligand²⁶. A sharp medium band appearing at 2690 cm⁻¹ is safely assigned to $\nu \text{S-CH}_3$ stretching vibration²⁷. This band gets shifted to lower frequency at 2660–2665 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra of complexes. It shows coordination through sulphur of thio ether group of Metribuzin to Cu²⁺. A tacit support for the above supposition regarding the coordination through the nitrogen of NH₂ group and sulphur of thio ether group each provided by the appearance of two new bands in far IR spectra of complexes. The weak band appearing at 505–510 cm⁻¹ is due to $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ and other at 400–405 cm⁻¹ is due to $\nu_{\text{Cu-S}}$ stretching vibration²⁸. Thus Metribuzin acts as a neutral bidentate ligand. The new bands appearing at 1490 cm⁻¹, 1380 cm⁻¹ and 1020 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of sum complexes show the presence of monodentate nitrate ion in the coordination sphere of these complexes²⁹. The new bands at 1560

and 1360 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra of a complex may be attributed to $\nu_{\text{asy}} \text{COO}^-$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{COO}^-$ vibration of acetate group. The difference between the two is nearly 200 cm⁻¹ which is typical to the monodentate coordination of acetate ion³⁰. The new bands appearing at 1180 cm⁻¹, 1080 cm⁻¹ and 625 cm⁻¹ are attributed to ν_4 , ν_1 and ν_3 modes of vibration of monocoordinated ClO₄⁻ ion in sum complexes.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra :

The magnetic moment of copper(II) complexes are found in the range of 1.89–1.91 B.M. (mentioned in Table 1) which are indicative of the fact that all the complexes are magnetically dilute and mononuclear. The values are slightly greater than μ_s value (1.732 B.M.) for one unpaired electron. This may be due to second order Zeemann effect³¹. The electronic spectra of these complexes display three bands which may be assigned to ${}^2A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and ${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ spin allowed transitions. The values of electronic bands and the various crystal field parameters derived from electronic spectra are given in Table 2.

These crystal field parameters are in good agreement with the values reported for tetragonally distorted octahedral complexes of Cu^{II}³².

Antihherbal activity of complexes :

The herbicidal effect of Metribuzin and its complexes of Cu^{II} has been studied on potato field. For this purpose potato field of one kattha (1369 sq. feet) has been prepared and post emergent herbicide Metribuzin was applied by dissolving its 7 g in 16

Table 2. Electronic bands (in cm^{-1}) and values of crystal field parameters

Complexes	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	D_q	D_s	D_t
[Cu(MBN) ₂ Cl ₂]	10950	13200	14380	1320.00	3032.5	1583.5
[Cu(MBN) ₂ Br ₂]	10880	13100	14300	1310.00	3020	1572
[Cu(MBN) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	13500	16350	17150	1635	3575	1985
[Cu(MBN) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂]	9300	11300	13250	1130	2812.5	1297.5
[Cu(MBN) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	14300	15750	17565	1575	4028.75	2057.25

gallon of water by protected spraying of the herbicide after 15 days the weed density, i.e. the amount of weeds per unit area was determined by counting. Similar process was applied for all the complexes of Cu^{II} with Metribuzin. The results are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Herbicidal effect of Metribuzin and its complexes with Cu^{II}

Compounds	% Decrease in weed density
Metribuzin	90–95
[Cu(MBN) ₂ Cl ₂]	92–97
[Cu(MBN) ₂ Br ₂]	92–96
[Cu(MBN) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	93–97
[Cu(MBN) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂]	91–95.6
[Cu(MBN) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	92–96.5

The result clearly shows that herbicidal character of Metribuzin gets enhanced in its Cu^{II} complexes.

Experimental

All the reagents used in synthesis are AnalaR grade. The precursor triazinone i.e. 4-amino-6-tert.-butyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazine-5-one was procured from a pesticide firm in China. Metribuzin was prepared from triazinone by refluxing 0.01 mole (about 2 g) of triazinone and 0.05 mole (0.65 g) of dimethylsulphate in alcoholic solution for 3 h followed by the addition of H₂SO₄ in it (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

White precipitated appeared which was filtered on suction pump and recrystallized in ethanol. It was dried in air oven and its melting point was recorded 124 °C which has been reported by NIOSH in 2001³³. The complexes were prepared by usual method of refluxing CuX₂ (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, CH₃COO⁻ and ClO₄⁻) salts with Metribuzin taken in 1 : 2 ratio in ethanol. The microanalysis for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen was carried out on Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN elemental analyzer. Copper was estimated volumetrically. Molar conductivity of complexes was measured on Elico conductivity bridge (Type CM 82T) using 10³ M DMSO solution. The magnetic moment of complexes was determined by Gouy balance at room temperature using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] (X_g = 16.44 × 10⁻⁶ CGS units) as the calibrating agent. The IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer in nujol while electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer of DMSO solution of complexes.

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